

30 years of public administration reforms: what does the Moroccan citizen think about it today?

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Résumé

La réforme de l'administration publique marocaine s'est transformée aujourd'hui en une obligation et un choix indiscutable du fait des progrès technologiques et de la mondialisation accrue qui ont rendu le citoyen marocain plus averti et plus éclairé sur ce que l'administration publique doit lui offrir comme service et dans quel cadre. Dans ce sens, le Maroc a entrepris depuis quelques décennies des efforts considérables dans le cadre de la modernisation de son appareil administratif. Cependant, le rythme de ses initiatives s'est rapidement amplifié lors de ces dernières années du fait du caractère urgent que représente la situation aujourd'hui. Un tel constat nous a amenés à poser des questions quant à la situation actuelle. Ainsi, nous nous sommes interrogés sur le sort de ses multiples initiatives. Ont-elles pu atteindre les objectifs escomptés et donc parle-t-on d'une administration publique moderne, efficace et efficiente capable d'offrir des services de qualité ? Ou bien s'agit-il encore d'une administration bureaucratique, régide, complexe, objet de pratiques non conformes. Ou bien se situe-t-elle entre les deux limites et suit-elle toujours sa voie vers le modèle escompté ?

Pour pouvoir répondre à ces questions, nous avons choisi de recourir à une étude qualitative via des entretiens semi-directifs réalisés auprès de 13 citoyens choisis après leur recours à quelques administrations publiques choisies au hasard. Le traitement et l'analyse des données collectées, assistés par le logiciel QSR Nvivo 11, nous ont permis de constater que les réformes administratives entreprises n'arrivent toujours pas à atteindre les objectifs qu'elles se sont fixés et continuent toujours leur chemin. Cependant, les mêmes résultats ont pu démontrer que la situation s'est largement modifiée par rapport à quelques décennies auparavant.

Mots clés : administration publique, réforme administrative, nouveau management public, citoyen, qualité.

Abstract

The reform of the Moroccan public administration has today become an obligation and an indisputable choice due to technological advancements and increased globalization, which have made the Moroccan citizen more aware and informed about what public administration should offer them in terms of services and in what framework. In this regard, Morocco has undertaken considerable efforts over the past few decades to modernize its administrative apparatus. However, the pace of its initiatives has rapidly increased in recent years due to the urgent nature of the situation today. Such a finding led us to ask questions about the current situation. Thus, we questioned the fate of its multiple initiatives. Have they been able to achieve the expected objectives and therefore is there talk of a modern, efficient, and effective public administration capable of offering quality services ? Or is it still a bureaucratic, rigid, complex administration, subject to non-compliant practices ? Or is it situated somewhere between the two extremes and still following its path towards the desired model ?

To answer these questions, we chose to conduct a qualitative study through semi-structured interviews carried out by 13 interviewees selected after their interaction with a few randomly chosen public administrations. The processing and analysis of the collected data, assisted by the QSR Nvivo 11 software, allowed us to observe that the administrative reforms undertaken still do not achieve the objectives they have set and continue on their path. However, the same results were able to demonstrate that the situation has largely changed compared to a few decades ago.

Keywords : public administration, administrative reform, new public management, citizen, quality.

Introduction

All over the world, the issue of public administration reform has been transformed in recent decades from a critical, urgent, and indispensable need for the adoption of reform processes and relevant mechanisms to an easier situation marked by a relatively less important need following the crossing of several steps, certainly at distinct levels between countries, but which have all led to the profound transformation of the public sector in general and public administration in particular.

In Morocco, the theme of public administration reform very quickly took center stage to the extent that, just after its independence, the Kingdom fixed an ambition to develop its own public administration model in accordance with the particularity of the Moroccan case. Since then, initiatives have been made succeeding one another, and efforts have multiplied in order to equip the country with a public administration capable of guaranteeing the exercise of the activities and missions assigned to it. However, the kingdom has witnessed in recent decades remarkable progress emerging on several fronts—economic, political, and relatively less social—following multiple initiatives and strategies undertaken in its quest for a developed Morocco. These multiple advances, which have been made at a pace far exceeding the goal of the public administration modernization itself, have once again brought to the surface the issue of equipping itself with an effective and efficient public administration capable of facing multiple challenges.

Thus, as everywhere else, the efforts made to modernize public administration date back to several years and continue to be the subject of several policies and strategies made in order to achieve the objectives expected by decision-makers. Hence, in recent years, this project has taken an essential place in the list of prerogatives of successive governments. Faced with an increasingly turbulent environment, the citizen is more informed than ever thanks to remarkable technological progress. It has become imperative for each country wishing to thrive in progress to have an efficient, modern, responsive public administration focused on the citizen, who must be considered as "customer".

As part of this research work, we will try to focus on this project's present state from the point of view of the one who is the current user, namely the Moroccan citizen. The efforts made and the initiatives undertaken are, of course, of great magnitude, except that this alone cannot give a clear and precise idea of the state we have reached today. Hence, the importance given to this vision that we will try to materialize on the ground through a qualitative study. A study based on semi-directive interviews directed to a representative sample of citizens. The results obtained

will be analyzed through the NVivo software in order to highlight the main orientations and provide answers to our initial questions.

To reach that point of our study, we will first try to describe, briefly, the main orientations that have accentuated the importance given to the issue of public administration reform and the need to make it an essential project of a strategic nature. Then, we will try to describe the main lines of reform adopted and launched by decision-makers with the aim of providing the Kingdom of Morocco with a modern and efficient public administration.

1. Theoretical background

For several decades, public administration reform has been an essential project for public decision-makers, which requires special attention and considerable determination. Since the first initiatives were launched, the results have always been far from aspirations due to multiple constraints, whether political, structural, cultural, legal, or even economic. If this has been somehow tolerable, today it is no longer the case since the world is no longer the same. Today, thanks to technological progress that has made the circulation of information more simple, having facilitated the means of communication throughout the world. Together with the recurring crises of public finances and the change in citizens conduct who have become more informed, states have no choice but to have an efficient, quality public administration capable of providing public services that meet the needs of their citizens.

1.1 The main orientations of the new need for public administration reform.

The new need for a significant reform of public administration generally dates back to the early 1980s. It has its origins in a multitude of factors that have all contributed to its triumph. In this sense, we will try here to present chronologically the main reasons that have led countries to make the reform of their public administrations a priority.

1.1.1 The rise of NPM ideas

Considered to be the main reasons behind the emergence of this new need for the reform of public administration in particular and the public sector in general, the movement of New Public Management, commonly known as (NPM), has redefined the rules of the game and has contributed significantly to the questioning of the basic principles and rules governing the management mode within public administration.

"Developed throughout sedimentation and successive layers, a true doctrinal puzzle", this current of New Public Management has established "new ways of thinking about administrative organization, based on a heterogeneous set of axioms, drawn from economic theories, management knowledge prescriptions, descriptions of practices tested in reforms (particularly

in Anglo-Saxon countries), together with systematizations produced by organizations such as the OECD" (Bezes, 2007, p. 18).

Based on a rich theoretical foundation that finds its arguments and foundations in various theoretical currents such as the neoliberalism of F.V. Hayek, the School of Public Choices indoctrinated by the work of Anthony Downs, Gordon Tullock, and James M. Buchanan, or the current of the sociology of organizations (Pesqueux, 2020), New Public Management will lead to a radical change in the way public organizations are managed. Stating that the idea is no longer a question of referring to the classic Weberian bureaucratic model, which is based on principles and foundations that make public administration a rigid, complex, inefficient mode of organization (Michaud, 2015) and unable to adapt to the new current context (Giauque & Emery, 2016), the so-called 'New Public Management' has very quickly put in place the necessary ingredients that will have to be guaranteed if we want to have an effective and efficient, modern public administration capable of responding adequately to the constantly sacable needs and aspirations of citizens in an increasingly turbulent environment.

Thus, having become one of the main paths of reform adopted by the majority of countries aiming at having a suitable public administration, the principles of NPM will very quickly impose themselves everywhere in the world, including in the Kingdom of Morocco, following this path of reform and adapting its strategic orientations.

1.1.2 Remarkable technological progress

Among the most significant reasons behind the realization that a modern and efficient public administration is an absolute necessity and therefore that public administration reform has become more than ever an obligation and not a choice, as was the case before, is the unprecedented technological progress that has affected all aspects of life (Lau, 2004).

Due to technological progress having led to constant upheavals in societies, now information circulates more rapidly and the means of communication are constantly developing, things that have transformed the world into a small village in which everyone knows what is happening everywhere else. In such a context, the needs of citizens all over the world seem to be becoming the same, and the way to meet them can only be similar, apart from the particularities of each country, which are certainly not the same because of the particularity of each case, according to its history, its resources, and its positioning. In the same way, the expectations and aspirations of citizens all over the world are identical and must be taken into account by all governments.

In such a context, it has become imperative for each country to take into account the needs of the citizens who have become the focus and their aspirations and expectations. Stating that, as in the private sector, the success of any organization can only take place through a satisfied

customer. As a result, it was necessary to find the appropriate way to take account of the budgetary constraints as a factual reality on the one hand and, on the other hand, to succeed in presenting citizens with a quality public service in accordance with their expectations and aspirations. Hence the real need that has been expressed throughout the world for a reform of the public sector in general and of public administration in particular.

Morocco, like any other country, could not do without the advantages offered by rapid technological progress, but at the same time, could never neglect the place that the citizen now occupies in any reform strategy with the speedy rising demands (Azelmad 2024). It has therefore become entrenched among decision-makers that the adoption of administrative reform that takes into account the changes brought about by rapid technological progress at all levels is an indisputable choice that shall be supported with commitment and will.

1.1.3 The need to support political, economic, and social progress.

The Kingdom of Morocco has made remarkable progress in recent decades in several fields, particularly political, economic, and social, adopting multiple legal reforms, a multitude of social programs, and several large-scale economic and industrial projects. This has enabled it to become a country with "strong economic growth, characterized by a certain political stability as well as a strong extroversion of economic activity" (Abourabi, 2020, p. 32).

In recent years, the pace of these changes has accelerated, and ambitions have reached much more promising levels. Despite the multitude of heterogeneous events that the world is currently experiencing and which make it uncertain to predict with the required accuracy, public decision-makers still continue to invest in the major projects initiated in the context of promoting a modern Morocco.

However, this remarkable transitional trajectory that Morocco witnesses (*Centre d'Etudes Internationales*, 2009) can only succeed through a modern, effective, and efficient public administration that is solid and able to respond to the various constraints imposed in the context of a constantly changing environment. In this sense, the Kingdom of Morocco has been obliged to modernize its administrative apparatus and improve the governance of public services offered to both citizens and businesses (Chauffour, 2018).

Thus, these reasons, all combined, accompanied by other factors, have imposed on public decision-makers the need to restore importance to the reform of the public sector in general and of the public administration in particular in order to improve the governance concept (Bhuiyan 2023). The project of the public administration reform has therefore become the priority of priorities and will be positioned at the top of the prerogatives that need to be raised with so much seriousness and involvement on the part of all stakeholders.

1.2 The main lines of the Moroccan public administration reform

Aware of the restrictive nature of the reform of the public administration, the Kingdom of Morocco started, several years ago now, several projects seeking to modernize its administrative apparatus. The objective is to have a modern, effective, and efficient public administration capable of dealing with the increasingly diverse needs of Moroccan citizens and overcoming the successive fluctuations in the environment in which it operates. Thus, this reform attempt has taken the form of several initiatives launched within the framework of multidimensional strategies and plans seeking to involve all stakeholders. As part of this research, we will try to look back at some large-scale initiatives and strategies.

The adoption of the Good Management Pact (PBG)/GMP in 1998 reflected the firm will and commitment of the Kingdom of Morocco to give substance to its new policy of change through a number of sectoral, specific, and long-term initiatives. This, and according to the expected objectives, had the new direction of laying the foundations of a new modern, efficient, and economical public administration, always concerned with its surroundings.

This was decided in the context of a new context marked by the increased economic globalization and the increase in trade between countries, accompanied by the unbridled competitiveness it has implied and, above all, the increasing needs and aspirations of citizens. Aware of the situation, the Kingdom of Morocco had thus paved the ground for the implementation of a new strategic approach to the reform of the public administration based on restructuring and the regeneration of the public administration as well as on innovation in the mechanisms of its functioning and flexibility in its organizational culture as a whole. The Pact was thus based on three important components, which are :

- The commitment to the moralization of administrative life ;
- The commitment to the rationalization of public management ;
- The commitment to strengthening communication, consultation, and opening up the administration to its environment.

1.2.2 The Economic and Social Development Plan (2000-2004)

As part of the ongoing efforts to reform its administrative system, the Kingdom of Morocco adopted the Economic and Social Development Plan (2000-2004). The plan, which had a comprehensive scope covering both economic and social aspects, gave the issue of public administration reform an important interest since, without a modern, efficient, and efficient administration, economic progress and social growth could not be achieved.

The adopted administrative reform had focused on deconcentration, sanitation, rationalization of management, and improvement of the administration's relations with users. The necessary

measures had been taken to modernize the tools of work, to strengthen the use of information technology, to rationalize human resources management, to improve the morality of public life, and to adopt systems and methods for monitoring and evaluating development policies and programs. The plan, had focused on the following aspects :

- Bringing the public administration closer to the citizens ;
- Increased rationalization of human resources management ;
- Improving the capacity of the administration.

1.2.3 The Public Administration Reform Support Program (PARAP)

In 2003, the Moroccan government adopted a broad program of public administration reforms designed to be implemented over several years with the support of the African Development Bank, the World Bank, and the European Union. This program, spread over four tranches, aimed to ensure the modernization of Moroccan public administration.

Thus, the program called PARAP (Support Program for Public Administration Reform) was structured into successive operations to support public administration reform. The first (PARAP I) was launched in 2003, and the measures taken as well as the reforms implemented contributed to laying the first milestones in a process of modernization of public administration. The second (PARAP II) was launched in 2006. It was part of the general framework of upgrading the Moroccan economy and aimed at consolidating the achievements of PARAP I in order to enable the reform to reach a more advanced level in accordance with the gradual approach adopted by the government and in particular the improvement of the efficiency of public administration. The third phase, named (PARAP III), launched in 2008, aimed to consolidate the achievements of PARAP I & II which were generally recognized as satisfactory in execution by the three international financial institutions that supported them. Seeking to achieve more coherence, the third program envisaged the extension to other ministries of the implementation of tools such as the globalization of credits and deconcentration schemes, as well as the redeployment exercise of civil servants. PARAP IV, adopted in 2010, sought in turn to improve the efficiency of the state in the management of budgetary and human resources, to consolidate and control the public wage bill, and to simplify administrative procedures through the development of the electronic administration.

1.2.4 Launch of the National Administration Reform Plan (PNRA)

The implementation of this strategic plan context comes down to the fact that even if Morocco has made considerable gains on the political and economic levels, it is important to state that its development model still remains far from aspirations and expectations. This discordance between political and economic progress on the one hand and achievements on the societal level

is manifested by the inability of public administration to keep pace with progress, together with that of the social changes that took place during the recent decades. These changes, which have developed following technological advances in recent years, have given rise to a new category of citizens who are now more informed than ever, with constantly changing needs and aspirations. Faced with such a constraint marked by the structural dysfunction of Moroccan public administration, generally inspired by the traditional bureaucratic model, it was necessary to intervene through a large-scale initiative seeking to confront the multiple obstacles. The objective is to move from a rigid, complex, and inefficient public administration towards an effective and efficient, flexible administration. Thus, the initiative took the form of a reform, which is characterized by a global and integrated change articulated around four complementary structural transformations. All of these transformations are ensured by a mixture of twenty-four structuring projects, as demonstrated in the following table :

Table 1: 24 PNRA projects

Organizational transformation (5 projects) :

- Adoption of the Deconcentration Charter ;
- Revision of the definition of the organizational rules of ministerial departments regulatory framework ;
- Implementation of the National Reception Improvement Program ;
- Upgrading public institutional communication of Public Administrations ;
- Restructuring of the Ministry of Administration Reform and Civil Service.

Managerial transformation (10 projects) :

- Adoption of the Public Services Charter ;
- Management by skills ;
- Restructuring of the upper and middle civil service ;
- Development of the system of access to public employment ;
- Development of the civil servant evaluation system ;
- Implementation an action plan of the Strategy for the Institutionalization of Gender Equality in the Public Service ;
- Strengthening social protection for civil servants ;
- Create an observatory for the Administration human resources ;
- Implementation of the public services improvement program ;

- measuring the quality of public services.

Digital transformation (5 projects) :

- Development of a Master Plan for the Digital Transformation of Public Administration ;
- Establishment of the “Government Gateway” platform ;
- Develop a Complaints and Grievances Management System ;
- Establishment of the Human Resources Management Information System for Public Administrations (HRIS-AP) ;
- Digital maturity of public services

Ethical transformation (4 projects) :

- Monitoring the implementation of National Anti-Corruption Strategy Projects ;
- Administrative time management in administrative departments and services ;
- Application of the law on the right of access to information ;
- Adoption of a national Open Government Action Plan.

Source : National Administration Reform Plan 2018 – 2021

1.2.5. Simplification of administrative procedures.

Faced with the complexity and “heaviness” of administrative procedures that have long marked the Moroccan administrative model, public decision-makers found themselves faced with the need to undertake considerable efforts to simplify and facilitate administrative procedures. The objective is to make quality public services available to both citizens and businesses, offered within a fair and reasonable timeframe in return for the least effort possible. In this sense, and in order to restore the connection between the administration and the Moroccan citizen and to sustain economic growth, the Kingdom of Morocco has launched since the end of the 1990s successive initiatives of reform based on the simplification of administrative procedures as a whole (OECD, 2023). Among the main initiatives is the approval of Law No. 55-19 related to the simplification of procedures and administrative formalities, which entered into force on September 28, 2020.

According to the ministry in charge of implementing this law, it aims, among others, to restore meaning of trust to the relationship that must link the administration to citizens, to simplify administrative procedures and formalities by eliminating those considered unnecessary, to set for most administrations a strict deadline for responding to requests from both citizens and businesses related to administrative acts, to improve the quality of services offered by administrations through the use of technology, and finally, to motivate all administrations to inform citizens or businesses concerned to know the reasons in case of rejection through presenting justifications.

1.2.6 The Public Services Charter.

In order to evolve the culture and practices of Moroccan public administration in the context of the provision of public services to citizens, Law No. 54.19 on the charter of public services was adopted and published on July 22, 2021. This landmark initiative has constituted the basis of a reference framework guiding all public administrations in the manner in which they must act. The novelty of such an initiative is evident in the establishment of a national system applicable to all administrative entities, whatever their origins. Thus, unlike previous strategies, which were marked by fragmented initiatives seeking to propose instruments for measuring and monitoring the quality of services provided by each administration separately, the new Charter imposes the bases of a new administrative model marked by uniform principles and operating rules. This new initiative, and in order to learn from previous failure initiatives, stands out by a set of features, including its binding nature mentioned in Article 3 of Law 54-19 related to the Public Services Charter, which stipulates that all government authorities are “required to comply with the content of this charter and to work to take all measures necessary for its implementation.”

The efforts made within the framework of the reform of Moroccan public administration are considerable and demonstrate the desire of the Kingdom of Morocco to have a quality public administration capable of meeting new challenges and satisfying, in the best possible conditions, the needs and expectations of both citizens and businesses. However, the question that arises is whether these successive initiatives were really able to achieve the expected objectives, or is it a vicious circle that continues to revolve following the failure and non-achievement of the latter? To answer this question, we proposed a set of hypotheses that we will try to confirm or refute during the remainder of this research work. These are the following hypotheses :

H1: The Kingdom of Morocco, following multiple initiatives launched over time, still cannot establish a quality public administration capable of responding adequately to the needs of citizens and businesses;

H2: The Kingdom of Morocco, following multiple initiatives launched over time, manages to develop an administrative model relatively consistent with the expectations and aspirations of citizens and businesses;

H3: The Kingdom of Morocco, following multiple initiatives launched over time, managed to develop an administrative model that was able to achieve all of the objectives set by public decision-makers.

2. Research methodology

Today, the observation is clear. The question of reforming the administrative apparatus is no longer a luxury choice but rather an undeniable necessity. With the rise of new public management ideas (Huron & Spindler, 2019), the public sector in general and public administration in particular can no longer be managed as it was decades ago. In Morocco, as in other countries, the reform of public administration is placed at the top of priorities. The initiatives launched in this regard are numerous and date back more than three decades now. However, the pressing question is whether these initiatives have been able to change the way public administration is managed and, consequently, whether they have achieved the expected objectives. In order to answer such questions, we have chosen the following conceptual framework :

Figure 1: The conceptual framework.

Source: developed by the researchers.

As a result, addressing these questions involves putting forward various possible hypotheses by drawing on existing theory. In our case, we consider that Morocco, through its various initiatives that have succeeded one another over the years, has managed to achieve the objectives set in advance and therefore now has a public administration that meets the requirements established by the new managerial theoretical framework, largely inspired by the NMP. Or he may have achieved some objectives while others are still unmet due to constraints, whether internal or external, that were not taken into account. Or, despite the various initiatives launched, his public administration still fails to move away from the increasingly contested traditional bureaucratic model, both by practitioners and by theorists in the field of public management.

Thus, through a purely qualitative approach that involves explaining and better understanding the different aspects of a phenomenon without relying on statistical data and therefore without quantification (Lejeune, 2019), we turned to the target population concerned by means of semi-structured interviews. The choice of the qualitative approach is not random but rather due to the nature of the research question and the particularity of the phenomenon being studied. Consisting of a set of "interpretative techniques that seek to describe, decode, translate, and generally uncover the meaning rather than the frequency of certain phenomena" (Coutelle, 2005, p. 2), this method will allow us to tie together data that cannot be identified by quantitative methods (Yin, 2009), while also granting us the opportunity for a better understanding of the phenomenon studied through direct contact with the target population.

The choice of semi-structured interviews as a means of data collection is due to the fact that it is a method that allows more flexibility for the respondent, enabling them to express themselves better, which will have a positive impact during the data processing phase (Gavard-Perret et al., 2012). During this research work, we conducted interviews with a sample of thirteen people (Table 1) from different age groups, genders, educational levels, and occupations. The goal is to allow for greater representation of the population.

Table 2 : The composition of our sample

Interview	reference	Gender	Age	Level of education	Position
1	A	Man	24	High School	Student
2	B	Man	28	Master's degree	Employee
3	C	Woman	62	Bachelor's Degree	Retired
4	D	Man	46	Bachelor's Degree	Merchant
5	E	Man	58	Secondary education	Farmer
6	F	Woman	52	High school	Saleswoman
7	G	Man	45	High school	Entrepreneur
8	H	Man	61	High school	retired
9	I	Man	35	Bachelor's Degree	Civil servant
10	J	Man	53	Bachelor's Degree	Farmer
11	K	Man	65	High school	Merchant
12	L	Woman	45	High school	Civil Servant
13	M	Man	35	Bachelor's Degree	Merchant

Source : developed by the reserchers

It should be noted that semi-structured individual interviews were conducted with a sample of thirteen people, consisting of ten men and three women, during their presence in various public administrations selected based on the level of attendance. Once collected, the data were processed and analyzed using QSR NVivo 11 software.

3. Results and discussion

In this part of the work, which constitutes the most important phase, we will review the main results obtained after processing the data from the semi-structured interviews conducted with our baseline sample, the characteristics of which have been previously mentioned. Once the results are presented, they will subsequently be the subject of discussions in order to provide suitable answers to our research hypotheses as well as to our fundamental question.

3.1 Results and discussion of textual analysis

As part of this purely qualitative research work, we focused more on textual analysis, as it is an important technique that will allow us to derive from the responses of the interviewed individuals an idea about the general orientation regarding their conception and perception of the impact of the various reforms undertaken within the framework of the modernization of the Moroccan public administration. In this sense, and in order to extract the maximum amount of information, we first focused on the study of word frequency, as it is a means that will allow us to detect the basic orientations. Through the use of the QSR Nvivo 11 qualitative data processing and analysis software, we have obtained the following results :

Figure 2 : Word Frequency Query.

Source : developed by us using QSR Nvivo 11

Table 3 : Frequency of the most cited words.

Word	Number	Percentage (%)
public	93	5,74
administration	68	4,19
services	41	2,53
citizens	36	2,22
relationship	24	1,48
reform	16	0,99
needs	15	0,93
state	13	0,80
portals	12	0,74
provided	12	0,74
technological	12	0,74
civil	11	0,68
quality	11	0,68
reality	11	0,68

Source : developed by us using QSR Nvivo 11

A preliminary breakdown of the most frequently mentioned terms leads us to conclude that public administration is an important subject for the interviewees and therefore for the Moroccan citizen in general, who considers this structure as an indispensable entity that they most often turn to in their daily lives. Just like the public administration, the services offered by this entity are at the heart of the central concerns of the Moroccan citizen, who believes it is time for these services to be of better quality, in line with their needs and future aspirations. In this sense, it is important to specify that the Moroccan citizen, with technological progress and globalization that have made the world a small village, has become more aware and more informed about what is happening around them and thus more demanding regarding what the administration offers them.

Other than public administration and services, the term relationship has been mentioned quite frequently, which suggests that the Moroccan citizen is questioning the nature of the relationship that connects them to public administration and therefore demands that such a relationship be reviewed in order to ensure mutual respect and increased consideration for the citizen who has now become a client. In the same context, the term need appears repeatedly,

which means that the interviewees express a lack of satisfaction and therefore demand that the public service offered and its delivery method be reviewed in order to ensure a significant degree of satisfaction. We are talking here about the compatibility between the service offered and the need to be met. The results obtained from the textual analysis clearly express that the Moroccan citizen has reached a significant degree of maturity regarding the issue of the necessity to reform public administration. The same results indicate that concerns are still present regarding the way the public administration acts when the circumstances are no longer the same, which requires an urgent rectification of the situation.

3.2 Results and discussion of thematic analysis.

Thematic analysis is a typical qualitative research method that relies on the analysis and interpretation of data collected by "themes." (Sabry, 2024). It aims to identify content indicators in qualitative data that can support or answer the research question and to organize them analytically in order to extract meaning. (Broc et Caumeil, 2018). As part of our research work and in order to address our problem and thus our fundamental research question, we have decided to focus on five important axes, which are : knowledge of basic concepts ; the reception within the public administration ; appreciation of the public service provided ; the digitization of the public offering.

Thus, the thematic analysis conducted using the QSR Nvivo 11 software allowed us to obtain the following results :

Table 4 : Cross-Tabulation of Thematic Analysis

	Knowledge of basic concepts	The reception within the public administration	Appreciation of the public service provided	The digitization of the public offering
A	<p>A public administration is a space where there are civil servants who ensure the delivery of public services.</p> <p>A public service is an act carried out by a public administration towards citizens.</p>	<p>It is a well-located administration situated in the city center, with a designated waiting area, offices displaying their specialties, and a security officer to guide citizens.</p>	<p>Normally, public administration should serve the citizen to meet their needs effectively. There must be trust between the two parties.</p> <p>Generally, the relationship between the citizen and the administration is not based on total trust, as the citizen is not</p>	<p>The public administration uses new technologies to provide remote public services instead of requiring individuals to visit the offices each time.</p> <p>Use online services, but only if they are in a secure and easy-to-understand</p>

	<p>A civil servant is a person who works on behalf of the state and ensures the delivery of public services.</p> <p>an operation through which one seeks to change the way a public administration is managed in order to deliver quality public service.</p>	<p>The reception cannot be disputed by the official who is doing their job well.</p> <p>the time needed to provide the service with an appropriate response to all my questions.</p>	<p>served in the best possible way by the official who works at their own pace.</p> <p>If the service is not satisfactory, I will go to the head of public administration to express myself and understand the reasons for the dissatisfaction.</p>	<p>framework and that the counterpart is not a significant amount to pay.</p> <p>several portals designed to facilitate the completion of administrative tasks. It's generally interesting because it gives you a clear idea of the service and the part that will make it happen.</p>
<p>B</p>	<p>a public institution that provides and implements a public service for the benefit of citizens, as is the case with local authorities. It is indeed a manifestation of the exercise of public authority.</p> <p>any activity of a public administration aimed at meeting a need of general interest.</p> <p>A person who holds a position within a public administration.</p> <p>It is a change made to improve the functioning of an administration and its service, and to adapt to</p>	<p>A bureaucratic administration with rather lengthy procedures.</p> <p>A normal welcome, but a long wait time.</p> <p>No.</p>	<p>A relationship of trust and cooperation.</p> <p>A relationship more of mistrust than of trust, of doubt as well as apprehension.</p> <p>Yes, without a doubt.</p> <p>It shows good signs, especially in terms of the digitalization of several services.</p>	<p>It is no longer a choice, but a necessity. This transformation is still slow.</p> <p>Yes, indeed, we have witnessed the digitalization of certain public services from several Moroccan administrations and the establishment of portals, particularly for complaints.</p> <p>for digital services, as they save you from traveling and waiting, and also help reduce response times.</p> <p>I can describe them as being out of reach for the general public they are intended for. Indeed, a large proportion of</p>

	<p>environmental and technological changes.</p>			<p>this public does not have a good grasp of computer tools.</p>
C	<p>A public administration is an effective, transparent body that is always at the service of the citizen.</p> <p>A public service is a provision provided by the state to meet the needs of citizens.</p> <p>A civil servant is a servant of the public interest employed by the state.</p> <p>An administrative reform is a process aimed at improving the efficiency of public administration.</p>	<p>The organization of public administration is clear, but it lacks modernization.</p> <p>The reception within the public administration is generally formal and quick.</p> <p>Not often I do feel rushed.</p>	<p>The relationship between public administration and the citizen must be based on trust.</p> <p>In reality, the relationship between public administration and the citizen is better than it was 10 years ago, although it can still be improved further.</p> <p>When a public service does not satisfy me, I often turn to the person in charge, even if it causes me problems.</p> <p>The new directions of the public administration reform aim to improve efficiency and transparency.</p>	<p>Technological transformation is something necessary as it simplifies our daily lives.</p> <p>Public administration benefits from this technological transformation that facilitates communication between citizens and the administration through online platforms.</p> <p>I choose public administration because it feels safer for me.</p> <p>Yes, I know those portals that are efficient, fast, and help avoid waiting in line.</p>

D	<p>For me, a public administration is an entity that must ensure equality of services and act with integrity.</p> <p>Public service refers to any activity or service provided by authorities to fulfill social missions.</p> <p>A civil servant is a person who works for the public administration.</p> <p>a process that involves adapting public services to the new needs of citizens.</p>	<p>The public administration is efficient, but the reception could still be improved.</p> <p>I find the reception rather impersonal, but efficient.</p> <p>It often depends on the moments and the agents.</p>	<p>The relationship between public administration and the citizen should be one of clear and open communication.</p> <p>In reality, the relationship between public administration and the citizen is based on communication, transparency, and access to information.</p> <p>The efforts to reform public administration are there, but we must wait to see the concrete results.</p>	<p>For me, technological transformation is concerning and raises ethical questions.</p> <p>Absolutely. Digitalization improves access to and transparency of public services.</p> <p>I choose online services to avoid unnecessary trips.</p> <p>Yes, these portals facilitate access to online public services.</p>
E	<p>A public administration is a modern entity, focused on innovation and accessible to everyone.</p> <p>A public service is a general interest activity managed by the State.</p> <p>It is a public official responsible for implementing state policies.</p> <p>reorganization of public structures aimed at making</p>	<p>The public administration is functional, but there are improvements to be made in terms of efficiency and speed of service.</p> <p>I have often been welcomed with professionalism, but without much warmth.</p>	<p>A relationship based on easy access to information.</p> <p>In reality, the relationship is satisfactory with a service provided within the standards.</p> <p>Not always for reasons like lack of time or trust in the person in charge.</p> <p>I'm not sure this will come to fruition, as previous reforms have not been effective.</p>	<p>Inevitable in that it will shape our way of living in the future.</p> <p>Yes, it allows for more efficient resource management through automation.</p> <p>I choose administration because you can get direct explanations.</p> <p>portals to better understand administrative procedures</p>

	them more modern and more efficient.	Sometimes, I find that insufficient.		and know the necessary information.
F	<p>an entity that must meet the needs of citizens and quickly adapt to challenges.</p> <p>A public service is a service provided by a public entity with the aim of meeting the needs of citizens.</p> <p>A civil servant is a state employee in the service of the public.</p> <p>an initiative to simplify and optimize administrative procedures.</p>	<p>The administration visited was well organized, but the wait times were a bit long.</p> <p>The reception varies, sometimes courteous, sometimes bureaucratic.</p> <p>Yes, I have always received the necessary attention.</p>	<p>The relationship must be based on mutual respect and collaboration.</p> <p>In reality, the relationship between the administration and the citizen has seen significant progress compared to previous years.</p> <p>Yes. To improve the quality of the service provided.</p> <p>The new directions must focus on adapting to the needs of citizens.</p>	<p>Technological transformation is important as it paves the way for new opportunities.</p> <p>Yes, because it reduces processing times and modernizes administrative processes.</p> <p>I prefer digital services because they are faster.</p> <p>Yes, the platforms simplify administrative procedures remotely.</p>
G	<p>This refers to a set of administrative activities and services handled by state-owned agencies on behalf of the citizens.</p> <p>By public service, we refer to all the services provided to meet the essential needs of citizens.</p> <p>It is an administrative agent</p>	<p>Poor orientation : not answering the phone poses an obstacle for citizens.</p> <p>The reception within the public administration has changed significantly. Now i feel like a considered citizen.</p>	<p>The reception within the public administration has changed significantly : one now feels like a considered citizen.</p> <p>The relationship must be characterized by the right to access information, respect, transparency, and equality.</p>	<p>The technological transformation will enable the improvement of services, efficiency, and ease of obtaining documents.</p> <p>to minimize expenses and save time.</p> <p>I prefer to use digital services to avoid traveling and save time.</p>

	<p>who manages public services within an administration.</p>	<p>I don't feel like I have the time I need.</p>	<p>In reality, the relationship must be based on meeting the needs of citizens.</p>	<p>these are portals that allow citizens to get an idea of the administrative procedures to follow.</p>
<p>H</p>	<p>A public administration is an entity that must provide quality services to citizens at the right time.</p> <p>A public service is a service provided by a public administration to the requester.</p> <p>A civil servant is an agent responsible for carrying out a specific task within an administrative organization.</p> <p>The administrative reform is the result of a special study leading to the hoped-for goal of its initiators.</p>	<p>The public services provided by the public administrations I visited are in a state of continuous improvement.</p> <p>We are welcomed by an agent who kindly directs us to the services related to our care.</p> <p>Yes, we are given the necessary time to meet our needs and address our requests.</p>	<p>The relationship between the administration and the citizen must be based on trust and mutual respect.</p> <p>In reality, the relationship between the citizen and the administration is entering a new phase characterized by mutual respect.</p> <p>Of course I am claiming to resolve my situation, but also to improve services for other citizens.</p> <p>The new directions of the reform should focus more on ongoing control and the improvement of the quality of civil servants.</p>	<p>Technological transformation is the sustainable and effective solution for all times, as it minimizes corruption and facilitates traceability.</p> <p>Not yet.</p> <p>I prefer to use digital services, as they save time and avoid trips to public administrations.</p> <p>Yes, I have an idea about the existence of such portals that are made available to citizens, except that it requires time and effort for them to be usable by the citizens.</p>

I	<p>A public administration is an organization that makes our daily lives easier through the services it provides.</p> <p>Set of tasks provided by the public authority to serve the needs of citizens.</p> <p>A person employed by a public organization.</p> <p>a process that involves improving the quality of services provided through the restructuring of the entity in question.</p>	<p>The administration undermines citizenship due to the attitudes of poorly placed officials.</p> <p>with negligence and inattentiveness.</p> <p>No, I am not given the necessary time.</p>	<p>The relationship must be based on respect with the aim of serving the common good.</p> <p>In reality, the relationship should be based on meeting the needs of the citizen.</p> <p>Yes, I'm trying to understand the reason.</p> <p>The new directions of the public administration reform are ambitious.</p>	<p>Technological transformation is important if it is used for the right purposes.</p> <p>No, we must first qualify the human element.</p> <p>Often, we avoid digital services due to a lack of trust.</p> <p>No i have no idea.</p>
J	<p>A public administration is an institution belonging to the State that is supposed to serve the needs of citizens through the provision of public services.</p> <p>A public service is a provision made by the state to citizens as part of the organization of people's daily lives.</p> <p>A civil servant is an agent who works on behalf of the State in various public</p>	<p>The visited public administration does not meet expectations, given the lack of organization and the absence of direction.</p> <p>Generally, the welcome is not up to par. One feels obliged not to take too much time to give others their turn.</p>	<p>The relationship should normally be in the direction of the citizen, who has now become a client, just like in a private company.</p> <p>In reality, we always find it difficult to assert ourselves against officials who often try to follow regulations without any room for maneuver.</p> <p>Yes, if it doesn't suit me, I take the initiative to speak with the person in charge.</p>	<p>Technological progress is a reality that has imposed itself and to which everyone must adapt.</p> <p>Yes, certainly, this way, we will have the opportunity to no longer have to move around all the time and even to have fair treatment.</p> <p>If the online public service is suitable and easy to use, I choose it.</p> <p>Yes, I am aware of the</p>

<p>administrations.</p> <p>a process of change initiated by leaders with the aim of improving the performance of public administrations.</p>	<p>Not enough time to handle things properly.</p>	<p>Initiatives often try to introduce a change for the better.</p>	<p>existence of these portals that are available to everyone to get acquainted with administrative procedures.</p>
<p>K A public administration is an entity belonging to the State responsible for providing services to citizens.</p> <p>A public service is a provision offered by the public administration on behalf of citizens in order to meet their daily needs.</p> <p>A civil servant is an employee who works within a public administration responsible for delivering public services to citizens.</p> <p>An administrative reform is an action aimed at changing the structure or the way a public administration operates in order to improve the quality of the services provided.</p>	<p>The visited administration was well-organized, with a waiting area and an agent responsible for guiding citizens.</p> <p>The way we are welcomed varies from one administration to another, but generally, we notice a change in the behavior of the officials.</p> <p>Yes, generally, I take the time I need.</p>	<p>The relationship must be based on mutual respect, trust, and good professional conduct.</p> <p>In reality, this relationship still doesn't reach what we desire, but generally, it remains acceptable.</p> <p>Yes. If the argument of the official doesn't suit me, I look for the person in charge to better understand the situation.</p> <p>The new directions of the administrative reform must focus on bringing the administration closer to citizens, transparency, and equality in the treatment of citizens.</p>	<p>Technological progress is important insofar as it will change the way we act, thereby facilitating access to various services.</p> <p>Yes, absolutely, as this will allow him to save on costs, improve the quality of service, and ensure greater transparency.</p> <p>I prefer digital services as long as they are well updated with ease of access and use.</p> <p>Yes. I am aware of the existence of such portals that are made available to citizens to assist them in carrying out their transactions.</p>

L	<p>A public administration is an entity responsible for delivering public services to citizens.</p>	<p>The visited administration was well organized with orientation sheets and waiting areas.</p>	<p>The relationship between the administration and the citizen must be based on respect, transparency, and seriousness.</p>	<p>Technological progress is a revolution that has changed our way of thinking, our lifestyle, and our needs.</p>
	<p>A public service is what a public administration offers to citizens as part of its mission.</p>	<p>The reception is up to par, carried out by capable people.</p>	<p>In reality, the relationship between public administration and the citizen is relatively satisfactory, with respect from officials who are now at the service of the citizens.</p>	<p>Absolutely. Public administration must take advantage of technological progress to better serve citizens, ensuring greater transparency and fairness.</p>
	<p>A civil servant is an agent who works on behalf of the State within the public administration, responsible for delivering various services.</p>	<p>Yes, I take the time I need to complete my transactions and receive the service I require.</p>	<p>Not really, I'm just trying to understand why I can't have what I need.</p>	<p>For me. I prefer online service, but only if it is reliable, secure, and easy to use.</p>
	<p>An administrative reform is a desired change implemented within public administrations with the aim of altering the way they operate.</p>		<p>The new directions are moving towards greater transparency and fairness in the delivery of services by increasingly better-qualified personnel.</p>	<p>Yes. I have already used some portals that are very useful for citizens.</p>
M	<p>A set of legal entities that ensure the operation of public services.</p>	<p>A disorganized administration, negligence from citizens, and poor quality of service.</p>	<p>A relationship that respects the Quality Charter and is focused on satisfaction and trust.</p>	<p>It is beneficial for both parties that it is the citizen : it will facilitate access to services for them as well as for the administration.</p>
	<p>Any activity of a public administration aimed at meeting the needs of the general interest.</p>	<p>There is no reception, no one asks us what we need or directs us to the appropriate</p>	<p>A relationship marked by dissatisfaction.</p>	<p>Yes, digitalization will help streamline activities within the administration, bringing more organization to work, while respecting processing</p>
	<p>A person holding a position employed by a public</p>		<p>No, since the process will take time, will we receive feedback within a specific timeframe or not.</p>	

<p>administration.</p> <p>The reform generally aims to improve service delivery, the digitization of services provided by public administration, and the strengthening of public management.</p>	<p>person.</p> <p>The necessary time</p>	<p>A hope for achievement and continuous monitoring and control.</p>	<p>deadlines for services.</p> <p>Of course, the use of digital services makes it easier to access the requested services, saves time, and avoids the need to travel.</p> <p>No, we need to publish these portals to make them known to the citizens.</p>
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Source : developed by us using QSR Nvivo 11

3.2.1 Knowledge of basic concepts.

Knowledge of the basic concepts related to the issue of public administration reform is, in our opinion, an important element, as the degree of this mastery will allow us to have an idea of the level of maturity that the Moroccan citizen has reached following the succession of all the initiatives undertaken in this regard. Thus, the responses from the interviewed individuals allowed us to conclude that the Moroccan citizen has reached a fairly high level of maturity, enabling them to better understand terms such as public reform, public service, civil servant, and administrative reform, with specific details regarding the roles designated for each term. This observation allows us to conclude that, initially, the administrative reforms undertaken have been able to create a previously suitable and conducive environment for the acceptance of such initiatives and active involvement in a major undertaking like administrative reform. On the other hand, this same observation allows us to conclude that the reform of public administration is now an indisputable priority and no longer a matter of choice.

3.2.2 The reception within the public administration.

Reception within public administrations is also one of the main facets and one of the common points among the various initiatives undertaken as part of the Moroccan public administration reform. Therefore, we questioned ourselves on this matter in order to have a clear and precise idea of the progress made in this regard. The responses obtained allowed us, on the one hand, to conclude that the issue of reception within the various public administrations has clearly changed in recent years, as demonstrated by the response of one of the interviewees who said, "*The reception within the public administration has changed significantly Now i feel like a considered citizen*". Or the response from another person who mentioned that "*The way we are*

welcomed varies from one administration to another, but generally, we notice a change in the behavior of the officials". Other responses suggest that there is still work to be done despite the progress made, as is the case with the response of a person who said, "*The public administration is functional, but there are improvements to be made in terms of efficiency and speed of service*".

3.2.3 Appreciation of the public service provided.

The evaluation of the public service provided by our various public administrations constitutes the very core of our research question. In this context, it is for us to ask the interviewed individuals about their assessment of the various public services provided. The goal is to obtain a clear and precise vision of both the level of quality of the services offered and their ability to adequately meet the needs of the citizens.

The review of the various responses related to this aspect has allowed us to conclude that the citizen is now informed and enlightened about the nature of the relationship that should now connect them with the administration. If the current observation clearly shows that the relationship between the citizen and the administration has made significant progress in recent years, the majority of those surveyed speak of a relationship that must now be based on trust, communication, mutual respect, and the consideration of the citizen, who is now placed at the center of its interest. This is the case with a person who said that "The relationship between the administration and the citizen must be based on trust and mutual respect" or another person who stated that « The relationship should normally be in the direction of the citizen, who has now become a client, just like in a private company ».

Other than this point, the various responses clearly demonstrate that the Moroccan citizen is now capable of asking questions and inquiring with the authorities if the public services provided do not meet their needs, which clearly shows that things have reached a fairly high degree of maturity that can contribute to the improvement of public offerings.

3.2.4 The digitization of the public offering.

The digitalization of public services offered is another important aspect in the process of reforming public administration and improving its offerings. With technological progress, while on the one hand the citizen has become more aware and more informed than before, on the other hand, this constitutes an important opportunity for public administration to improve the quality of its services. The responses of the interviewed individuals clearly show that the Kingdom of Morocco has embarked on this new form of public offering, mentioning that several public administrations have indeed started to offer digitalized public services, as mentioned by one interviewee who said, " Generally, yes. The public administration uses new technologies to provide remote public services instead of requiring individuals to visit the

offices each time". Or another person who said : "Yes, indeed, we have witnessed the digitalization of certain public services from several Moroccan administrations and the establishment of portals, particularly for complaints". Something that will guarantee a quality public service with a high degree of equality in treatment, combating all forms of nepotism and corruption. In this sense, an interviewee said, "Absolutely. Digitalization improves access to and transparency of public services » or even « Yes, certainly, this way, we will have the opportunity to no longer have to move around all the time, and even to have fair treatment ».

Other than that, the responses demonstrated that most of the respondents are in favor of using the offered solutions by resorting to technology, provided that it is easy to handle, secure, and in exchange for a reasonable price, which clearly shows that the Moroccan citizen is now capable of resorting to the digitized offer, which is considered today as more profitable and more compatible with the needs of the citizens. The case is mentioned by an interviewee who stated that "For me. I prefer online service, but only if it is reliable, secure, and easy to use » or another person who said that « I prefer to use digital services, as they save time and avoid trips to public administrations ».

Conclusion

The reform of public administration has today become an indisputable process through which public administrations around the world must go in order to have an administrative apparatus capable of meeting challenges and facing increasingly imposing constraints both internally and externally. From now on, with technological progress that has facilitated communication, increased globalization that has made the world a small village, and the succession of budget deficits, the concern to modernize public administration has become one of the main priorities of public decision-makers.

In Morocco, the observation is the same. Public decision-makers have, for several decades, emphasized the necessity of reforming public administration in order to ensure support for the significant advances made in the political, economic, and social spheres. In this sense, several initiatives have been launched since the mid-1980s, with the aim of having a modern, efficient, and effective public administration capable of delivering quality services that meet the expectations and aspirations of the Moroccan citizen, who has now become the focal point.

The objective of this research work was to emphasize the achievements of the past thirty years of reform. Thus, the results obtained have shown that the Moroccan citizen, for their part, has already reached a high degree of maturity regarding the issue of reforming public administration while being open to the possibility of enriching public services through digitalization. The same results have noted that the Moroccan public administration is no longer the same as it was a few decades ago. Today, there is recognition of progress in the reception of citizens by public officials, who are beginning to regard citizens differently by offering them the attention they deserve. It is also recognized the imposition of new prerogatives guaranteeing greater efficiency in public action and the establishment of new provisions offering more equity in the treatment of citizens. In the same context, the digitalization of public services has reached a sufficiently advanced level, allowing citizens to benefit from technological advancements.

It should be noted that the results obtained did not reach a consensus among the respondents, as there are still cases that reflect a certain delay, whether related to the behavior of the officials or the low quality of the public service offered, which leads us to conclude that the lessons drawn from this research work are not entirely reversible. This observation is supported by the small number of respondents, which cannot reflect the situation as a whole.

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